

parts withered, dried, and ruptured along the streaks, causing a blighted appearance

The feeding activity of adult beetles was recorded at 0900, 1200, and 1600

hours on a clear, sunny day. Adult beetle feeding was maximum (44%) at 0900; it was lowest (3%) at 1200 and intermediate (26.8%) at 1600 hours.

major insect pests of irrigated rice are the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Smith and Abb.), the brown semilooper *Mocis latipes* (Guen.), the rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus* sp., and the stink bug *Oebalus poecilus* (Dall). These insect populations must be controlled if rice is to be grown profitably. The table shows pest occurrence in relation to the growth stage of the rice plant.

Major insect pests of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin

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About 4,000 ha of irrigated rice producing 2 crops/year is cultivated in the Jari estate on the northern side of the Amazon River, between the Paru and Jari Rivers. IR22 is commercially grown in the area. The first crop is planted in April–May and harvested in August–September, then the second crop is planted and harvested in December–January. Field operations are completely mechanized; large machinery and agricultural aircraft are used.

The cultivated area has increased in the past few years and the double-cropping system has recently been adopted. Consequently, insect pests are becoming serious. Field surveys show that the

Major insect pests of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin, Brazil.

Rice growth stage	Major insect pests		Damage
	1st crop	2d crop	
Seedling emergence to maximum tillering	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	<i>S. frugiperda</i>	Leaf feeding
	<i>Mocis latipes</i>	–	Leaf feeding
	<i>Lissorhoptrus</i> sp.	<i>Lissorhoptrus</i>	Leaf feeding (adults) and root pruning (larvae)
Panicle initiation to heading	<i>Mocis latipes</i>	–	Leaf feeding and head damage
Heading to dough	<i>Oebalus poecilus</i>	<i>O. poecilus</i>	Grain sucking (nymphs and adults)

Effects of granular insecticides on stem borers and their parasites and predators

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Granular insecticide formulations tend to be effective for the control of rice stem borers and brown planthoppers in Thailand.

An experiment was conducted at the Chainat Rice Experiment Station, Chainat province, to determine the effectiveness of granular insecticide formulations for stem borer control, their adverse effects on stem borer parasites and predators, and the expected monetary returns from treated vs check plots.

Three granular insecticides — lindane 6% G, chlorfenvinphos 10%, carbofuran 3% G — were tested on variety RD1, which is susceptible to stem borers. They were applied at 1 kg a.i./ha 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting.

A split-plot design with three replications was used, with insecticide rates as the main plot and insecticide as subplots. A compound fertilizer of

Table 1. Effects of granular insecticides applied at 1 kg a.i./ha 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) on stem borers, and that on predators and parasites. Chainat, Thailand, 1976.

Treatment	Effect of insecticide		
	20 DT	40 DT	60 DT
	<i>Stem borers</i> ^a		
Lindane	2.50	28.50	92.33
Chlorfenvinphos	3.33	22.00	32.00
Carbofuran	0.50	7.50	7.50
Check	7.67	41.83	17.00
LSD 0.05	NS	1.37	1.71
C.V.	57.0%	23.2%	19.1%
	<i>Predators</i> ^b		
Lindane	6.17	63.83	69.83
Chlorfenvinphos	9.83	43.83	38.17
Carbofuran	4.83	12.83	6.33
Check	15.17	56.00	85.67
LSD 0.05	0.85	1.00	1.09
C.V.	23.8%	12.6%	13.3%
	<i>Parasites</i> ^c		
Lindane	4.67	2.50	3.17
Chlorfenvinphos	5.33	4.83	6.00
Carbofuran	6.17	3.67	2.67
Check	8.50	6.83	6.50
LSD 0.07	0.53	NS	NS
C.V.	17.5%	2.7.0%	29.2%

^a Stem borer infestation based on % dead hearts. The predominant species of stem borer were *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) and *Chilo polychrysus* (Meyrick). ^b No./10 sweeps of sweeping net 42 cm in diam. The predators were *Tetragnatha* spp., *Oxyopes* spp., *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* (Reuter), *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, and damselflies. ^c No./10 sweeps of sweeping net 42 cm in diam. The parasites were *Telenomus* spp., *Apanteles* spp., *Tetrastichus* spp., *Elasmus* spp., and *Tropobracon* spp.

Table 2. Rice yield and monetary value in the plots treated with granular insecticides at 1 kg a.i./ha. Chainat, Thailand.

Insecticide	Rice yield (t/ha)	Income ^a (\$/ha)	Cost of insecticide (\$/ha)	Profit ^b (\$/ha)
Carbofuran	6.26	783	94	689
Chlorfenvinphos	5.44	680	127	553
Lindane	3.53	441	11	408
Check	3.38	423	—	423

^aValue of rice based on price of rice at \$125/t. ^bValue of crop (income) minus cost of insecticide and application.

16-20-0 NPK was applied at 375 kg/ha, split into 3 applications.

Carbofuran was the most effective insecticide against the stem borer and lindane the least effective (Table 1). The insecticides did not affect the number of

parasites but carbofuran severely reduced the predator population. The net increase from supplying carbofuran was about 61% more than from the untreated check (Table 2). ■

Soil and crop management

Effect of seed, seedbed, and main field treatments on the yield of ADT31 and IR20

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Two experiments on seed, seedbed, root nutrient treatments, and main field manuring were carried out at Ambasamudram during 1977 and 1978 kar (Jun–Sep). The 1977 experiment

Table 1. Effect of seedbed and main field manuring on grain yield of 25-day-old IR20 seedlings grown in a farmer's field, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1977 kar.

Treatment		Yield (t/ha)
Seedbed ^a	Main field ^b	
None		4.0
Diammonium phosphate		4.8
Diammonium phosphate	Recommended NK fertilizer (no phosphorus)	4.9
None	”	3.8
Diammonium phosphate	Recommended NPK	4.7
None	”	4.2

CD = 0.3

^aDiammonium phosphate treatment: 2 kg/40 m².

level. The 1978 experiment studied the combined effect of seed, seedbed, and root-dip nutrient treatments on the yield of the short-duration variety ADT31 transplanted at both 25 and 40 DS.

Seedbed manuring significantly affected the yield of IR20. The seedlings that received 2 kg diammonium phosphate/40 m² in the seedbed had 0.8 t/ha higher grain yield than the seedlings that did not (Table 1). Seedlings that received seedbed manuring but no phosphorus fertilizer in the main field yielded significantly more than the control (4.9 vs 3.8 t/ha) but about the same as the seedlings that received both seedbed manuring and main field phosphorus fertilizer application (4.7 t/ha). The finding suggests that seedlings treated with diammonium phosphate in the seedbed need no phosphate application in the main field.

The grain yield of ADT31 was significantly affected by 1) the interaction between seedling age at transplanting and seedbed manuring, 2) the interaction between seedling age

examined the combined effect of seedbed and main field manuring on the yield of IR20 transplanted 25 days after sowing (DS) into a field with low phosphorus

Table 2. Effect of seedbed, sprouted seed, and root-dip nutrient treatment on grain yield of ADT31 seedlings, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1977 kar.

Seedling age at transplanting (days after sowing)	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	Diammonium phosphate treatment ^a			Root-dip treatment ^b		
	2 kg/40 m ² to seedbed	3% soln to sprouted seed	None	4% manganese sulfate soln	3% zinc sulfate soln	None
25	6.1	5.7	5.2	5.8	5.6	5.5
40	5.4	4.9	5.1	5.4	4.6	5.4

^{ab}CD = 0.2

Table 3. Effect of seed and seedbed treatment on grain yield of 25-day-old ADT31 seedlings, Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1978 kar.

Seed	Treatment		Grain yield (t/ha)
	Seedbed	Sprouted seed	
1% potassium chloride soln			5.1
1% potassium chloride soln	2 kg diammonium phosphate/40 m ²		6.4
1% potassium chloride soln		3% diammonium phosphate soln	5.9
	2 kg diammonium phosphate/40 m ²		5.9
		3% diammonium phosphate soln	5.6
		Control	5.3

CD = 0.3